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Experimental physics goals documented in the form of presentations on Indico (Green). Contributions for Open Access proceedings publication with SN (Gold) approved. User community survey on R&D topics, priorities, and collaboration potentials considering geographical distribution and topical complementarity launched.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE PHYSICS CASE OF FCC	4
1.1. THE PHYSICS CASE FOR A LEPTON COLLIDER (FCC-EE)	4
1.2. THE PHYSICS CASE FOR A HADRON COLLIDER (FCC-HH)	5
2. OVERVIEW OF THE FCC PHYSICS CASE	8
2.1. OPPORTUNITIES & CHALLENGES AT A NEW FRONTIER COLLIDER	8
2.2. THE FCC-EE COLLIDER	9
2.3. PHYSICS OPPORTUNITIES	10
2.3.1. <i>Higgs boson properties</i>	10
2.3.2. <i>Precision measurements</i>	12
2.3.3. <i>Flavours</i>	15
2.3.4. <i>Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD)</i>	16
2.3.5. <i>Direct Observations of Feebly Coupling Particles</i>	16
2.4. CHALLENGES FOR THE DETECTOR DESIGN	18
2.4.1. <i>Detector Requirements</i>	18
2.4.2. <i>TeraZ Challenges</i>	19
2.4.3. <i>W Mass Determination</i>	19
2.4.4. <i>Flavour Challenges</i>	19
2.4.5. <i>Tau Physics</i>	19
2.4.6. <i>Rare Processes</i>	19

2.4.7.	<i>Integration Challenges</i>	20
2.5.	THE CASE FOR FOUR INTERACTION POINTS	20
2.6.	THEORETICAL CHALLENGES	20
3.	FCC-EE MIDTERM REPORT AND NEXT STEPS	21
4.	CONCLUSION	22
5.	REFERENCES	23

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE PHYSICS CASE OF FCC

1.1. THE PHYSICS CASE FOR A LEPTON COLLIDER (FCC-EE)

The Future Circular Collider (FCC) represents a groundbreaking step in particle physics, offering an unparalleled opportunity to explore the deepest questions about the universe. Following the discoveries made by the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), particularly the Higgs boson, the FCC aims to push the boundaries even further. It is designed to probe the Standard Model with unprecedented precision, exploring new physics at both low and high energies.

The project is divided into stages: FCC-ee, an electron-positron collider, will conduct high-precision measurements of the Higgs boson, electroweak gauge bosons, and the top quark. These measurements are critical for understanding the fundamental forces and particles that govern our universe. This collider is expected to offer sensitivity to processes from the early universe, potentially shedding light on the Brout–Englert–Higgs field and the electroweak phase transition.

The power of FCC-ee to probe the Higgs boson and other SM particles at a much higher resolution would allow physicists to peer further into the cloud of quantum fluctuations surrounding them. The combination of results from previous lepton and hadron colliders at CERN and elsewhere has shown that electroweak symmetry breaking is consistent with its SM parameterisation, but its origin (and the origin of the Higgs boson itself) demands a deeper explanation. The FCC is uniquely placed to address this mystery via a combination of per-mil-level Higgs-boson and parts-per-million gauge-boson measurements, along with direct high-energy exploration, to comprehensively probe symmetry-based explanations for an electroweak hierarchy. In particular, measurements of the Higgs boson’s self-coupling at the FCC would test whether the electroweak phase transition was first- or second-order, revealing whether it could have potentially played a role in setting the out-of-equilibrium condition necessary for creating the matter-antimatter asymmetry.

Figure 1: The FCC-ee baseline design luminosity summed over four (orange) interaction points as a function of centre-of-mass energy, also showing the luminosity typically achievable by linear colliders with a single interaction point. Credit: FCC study

The second stage, FCC-hh, a proton-proton collider, would dramatically extend the search for new particles, potentially discovering particles beyond the Standard Model, such as those associated with dark matter or other exotic phenomena. The FCC-hh could reach energies far exceeding those of the LHC, opening up new possibilities for direct discovery.

A larger 91 km version of the collider not only enables the reuse of the tunnel and infrastructure for a future 100 TeV hadron collider but also significantly broadens the FCC-ee's scientific scope beyond just studying the Higgs boson. The exceptional control over the center-of-mass energy, facilitated by resonant depolarization, combined with the unmatched luminosity offered by an FCC-ee with four interaction points, would lead to the production of approximately 6 trillion Z bosons, 240 million W pairs, 2 million Higgs bosons, and 2 million top-quark pairs. This would occur over a span of 16 years, representing an unprecedented advancement in particle physics that surpasses the capabilities of current facilities like the LEP/LHC tunnel, where such production levels are unachievable.

Furthermore, the Z-pole run opens doors to otherwise inaccessible studies in flavour physics (such as b and τ physics), Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), hadronization, searches for rare or forbidden decays, and the exploration of the dark sector. Following this, the W boson would be studied with unparalleled precision at the FCC-ee. Given its crucial role in the SM, strengthening our knowledge of the W boson's mass by an order of magnitude would allow for testing the SM at new quantum levels and exploring a wide range of new-physics models.

At the highest energy levels, the FCC-ee would also delve into physics related to the top quark, the heaviest known particle. The top quark's mass is pivotal for predicting SM processes and has significant implications for the cosmological fate of the vacuum. An improvement in precision by more than an order of magnitude would greatly enhance our understanding of the strong coupling constant and is essential for probing physics beyond the SM with unprecedented accuracy.

1.2. THE PHYSICS CASE FOR A HADRON COLLIDER (FCC-HH)

In terms of discovery potential, the FCC-hh collider would provide a direct exploration of new physics, probing for various resonances expected in new theoretical scenarios. Historically, increased precision has been a pathway to groundbreaking discoveries, such as those of the W and Z bosons, the top quark, and the Higgs boson. The FCC-ee's Z-pole run, a key highlight of the feasibility study, promises an extensive array of measurements with a 50-fold increase in precision compared to current capabilities. This would allow for a meticulous examination of the Z lineshape, electroweak observables, and crucial constants like the electromagnetic and strong coupling constants. Such precision would significantly constrain potential new physics, especially when compared to similarly precise predictions from the Standard Model (SM), marking a potential sevenfold increase in the energy scale explored—comparable to the leap from the LHC to the FCC-hh.

Figure 2: The FCC-hh discovery reach as a function of mass for various resonances expected in new physics scenarios.

The day FCC-hh directly finds a signal for beyond-SM physics, the precision measurements from FCC-ee will be essential to pinpoint its microscopic origin. Indirectly, FCC-hh will be sensitive to energies of around 100 TeV, for example in the tails of Drell–Yan distributions. The large production of SM particles, including the Higgs boson, at large transverse momentum allows measurements to be performed in kinematic regions with optimal signal-to-background ratio and reduced experimental systematic uncertainties, testing the existence of effective contact interactions in ways that are complementary to what is accessible at lepton colliders. Dedicated FCC-hh experiments, for instance with forward detectors, would enrich further the new-physics opportunities and hunt for long-lived and millicharged particles.

Figure 3: The FCC-ee's minimal potential physics program, depicted in green, outlines 15 years of operation with two interaction points, increasing in center-of-mass energy. The chart also shows the estimated number of events for Z, WW, ZH, and $t\bar{t}$ processes with four interaction points, highlighting the physics opportunities presented by additional possible center-of-mass energies, shown in orange. This plan underscores the significant scientific potential of the FCC-ee across different energy levels, offering diverse opportunities for discovery.

Additionally, the FCC program addresses critical open questions in physics, such as the matter-antimatter asymmetry, the nature of dark matter, and the peculiar structure of quark and lepton masses. The FCC's integrated approach, combining the strengths of both the FCC-ee and FCC-hh, offers the most comprehensive strategy to explore the unknown realms of particle physics, far surpassing the reach of any current or proposed collider. FCC physics reach are the origins of exotic astrophysical and cosmological signals, such as stochastic gravitational waves from cosmological phase transitions or astrophysical signatures of high-energy gamma rays. These phenomena, which include a modified electroweak phase transition, confining new physics in a dark sector, or annihilating TeV-scale WIMPs, could arise due to new physics which is directly accessible only to an energy-frontier facility.

The extensive detector capabilities, the detailed analysis tools, and the innovative approach to computing needs underline the project's ambition. By aligning these advancements with the infrastructure required for a future 100 TeV hadron collider, the FCC stands as a bold, long-term plan to lead particle physics into the next century. The FCC will provide a powerful platform for discovery and precision measurement that will shape our understanding of the universe at its most fundamental level.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE FCC PHYSICS CASE

2.1. OPPORTUNITIES & CHALLENGES AT A NEW FRONTIER COLLIDER

The concept of a high-luminosity Higgs and Electroweak factory emerged from a convergence of opportunities between 2010 and 2012. Initially, the goal of increasing hadron collider energy by an order of magnitude, up to 100 TeV, combined with the limitation of high-field magnets to under 16–20 T, spurred discussions about constructing a new ring with a circumference of 80–100 km. This size range proved optimal given the geographical layout around Geneva [1, 2].

The first indications of a light Higgs boson in the winter of 2011 [3, 4], followed by its discovery in 2012 around 125 GeV [5, 6, 7, 8], spurred interest in possibly rebuilding a collider within the LEP/LHC tunnel. Significant advancements in circular collider technology, exemplified by B factories like PEP-II, KEKB, and the new Super-B [9] and SuperKEKB [10] projects, made it feasible to design a collider with a luminosity exceeding at the cross-section maximum in multiple interaction regions [11].

Proposing a similar machine in a 100 km tunnel [12], which could eventually host a 100 TeV collider, was considered an appealing continuation of the LEP/LHC combination, leveraging synergistic infrastructure and a favourable funding profile, along with important fundamental physics complementarities. Coincidentally, a circumference of 80–100 km is necessary for a circular collider to reach the top quark pair production threshold, which is crucial for precision measurements in electroweak physics. Following the 2013 European Strategy for Particle Physics recommendations, the Future Circular Collider (FCC) conceptual design study was launched in February 2014, encompassing studies of both hadron and lepton colliders.

The Conceptual Design Reports [13, 14, 15], produced by a collaboration of 1,500 authors, outlined the FCC's integrated program (FCC-INT), a staged implementation plan in which the lepton collider (FCC-ee) would be the first to be installed in a new 100 km underground circular infrastructure. This approach would significantly contribute to the infrastructure needed for the 100 TeV collider, as illustrated in Fig. 1. FCC-ee could begin collecting data shortly after the completion of the HL-LHC, operating for about 15 years. This period would allow for the necessary R&D to develop mass-produced, cost-effective 16–20 T dipoles with the required accelerator-class quality and reliability. Subsequently, the installation of the 100 TeV hadron collider (FCC-hh) could occur during a 10-year shutdown following FCC-ee's operation. Cost estimates provided for each collider independently, as well as in the staged scenario, demonstrated a significant cost saving of 7 billion CHF in the integrated scenario. A comparison with other potential routes to a 100 TeV collider (e.g., low-energy hadron collider or linear colliders) can be found in Ref. [17] (see, for example, Sect. 23), which concluded that FCC-INT offers the most efficient pathway to implementing the FCC. The physics programs of both machines are complementary and synergistic, offering a powerful long-term vision for high-energy physics.

This vision was endorsed by the 2020 European Strategy for Particle Physics (ESPP) [18], which called for the preparation of a Higgs factory, followed by a future hadron collider capable of probing energy scales an order of magnitude higher than those of the LHC. The ESPP prioritized the technical and financial feasibility of the Future Circular Colliders as a top priority (after the HL-LHC) for CERN and its international partners. It emphasized that Europe, in collaboration with its international partners, should explore the technical and financial viability of a future hadron collider at CERN with a center-of-mass energy of at least 100 TeV, with an electron-positron Higgs and electroweak factory

as a potential first stage. This feasibility study should be established as a global effort, with the goal of completing it by the next Strategy update.

In June 2021, the CERN Council approved the FCC technical and financial feasibility study (FCC-FS), with a focus on the first step: the tunnel and the initial machine, FCC-ee. The study is expected to deliver its report (FCC-FSR) by the end of 2025. More information on the goals, milestones, and organization of the study can be found in Refs. [19, 20]. R&D on high-field magnets for FCC-hh is being conducted independently, with high priority, and significant funding from CERN has been allocated to both initiatives. The FCC technical and financial feasibility study was officially launched during the FCC-week from June 28 to July 2, 2021 [21].

2.2. THE FCC-EE COLLIDER

As highlighted in a 2013 study [22], the expected performance of the FCC lepton collider is exceptionally impressive, particularly in the energy range of the four high-mass particles of the Standard Model. The design, which draws inspiration from the B factories with features like top-up injection, strong focusing, and crab-waist optics, is optimized to fit within the same tunnel as the future 100 TeV hadron collider, as illustrated in Fig. 4. This configuration maximizes luminosity. With two independent 100-km-circumference rings, a fixed synchrotron power of 100 MW, and two interaction points (IPs), the collider can achieve an integrated yearly luminosity more than 100,000 times greater than that of LEP at the Z pole, as shown in Fig. 2. Additionally, the reduced beam energy spread, resulting from the large bending radius of the ring [23], enhances the natural build-up of transverse beam polarization, enabling highly precise beam energy calibration even at energies above the W-pair production threshold. The collider is also capable of operating across a broad energy range, extending up to and slightly beyond the top-pair threshold.

Figure 4: Schematics of the implementation of the FCC-ee collider (left) and the FCC-hh collider (right) in the common infrastructure [14]. The FCC-ee booster footprint coincides with that of the FCC-hh. The asymmetric lepton beam lines around the FCC-ee interaction regions are designed to minimise synchrotron radiation in the detectors.

The FCC-ee project will be rolled out in phases, focusing on exploring different areas of physics, including electroweak interactions, particle flavors, the Higgs boson, and the top quark. It will cover a wide range of energies, starting from the Z pole and WW threshold, going through the peak of Higgs production, and reaching up to the top quark production threshold and beyond. The collider's ability to achieve very high luminosity at the Z pole opens up exciting possibilities for discovering new

particles [25]. The planned 15-year research program is summarized in Table 1. Scientists are also looking into the potential to operate the collider specifically at the Higgs resonance at 125 GeV and the possibility of having four points where particles can interact.

Working point	Z, years 1-2	Z, later	WW, years 1-2	WW, later	ZH	$t\bar{t}$
\sqrt{s} (GeV)	88, 91, 94		157, 163		240	340–350 365
Lumi/IP ($10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	70	140	10	20	5.0	0.75 1.20
Lumi/year (ab^{-1})	34	68	4.8	9.6	2.4	0.36 0.58
Run time (year)	2	2	2	–	3	1 4
Number of events	6×10^{12} Z		2.4×10^8 WW		1.45×10^6 ZH +	1.9×10^6 $t\bar{t}$ +330k ZH 45k WW \rightarrow H +80k WW \rightarrow H

Table 1: The baseline FCC-ee operation model, showing the centre-of-mass energies, instantaneous luminosities for each IP, integrated luminosity per year summed over the 2 IPs corresponding to 185 days of physics per year and 75% efficiency.

At the Z pole and WW threshold, the FCC-ee provides unmatched precision in controlling the centre-of-mass energy and its distribution. This precision is achieved through a technique called resonant depolarization, which allows for incredibly accurate beam energy measurements with an accuracy of parts per million (ppm). This method is supported by a polarimeter that doubles as a beam spectrometer and by the detailed analysis of muon pairs produced in the experiments. These tools help monitor, with high precision, the difference in energy between electrons and positrons, the angle at which the beams cross, and the distribution of the center-of-mass energy. It has been demonstrated that at the Z pole, the centre-of-mass energy can be known with an accuracy of 1 ppm or better, with a point-to-point uncertainty of 40 keV and a spread within a couple of thousandths. This high level of precision is crucial for accurately measuring the Z boson mass and width, the forward-backward asymmetry of muon pairs near the Z pole, and the W boson mass.

These calibration techniques, while challenging, are essential for maintaining precise control over the center-of-mass energy, especially if the collider runs at the Higgs resonance. At higher energies, the processes involving ZZ, Z, and W allow for center-of-mass energy determination within a few MeV, using the Z and W masses measured at lower energies.

2.3. PHYSICS OPPORTUNITIES

2.3.1. Higgs boson properties

The initial idea behind the concept of a circular collider like FCC-ee was to build a high-luminosity Higgs Factory, designed to operate at the energy level where the ZH production process (where a Z boson and a Higgs boson are produced together) is at its peak. This process is further enhanced by another process, namely WW fusion, which also produces Higgs bosons and becomes more effective at higher energies (as shown in Table 1).

The total ZH cross-section can be determined independently of the Higgs boson detailed properties by counting events with an identified Z boson, and for which the mass recoiling against the Z clusters around the Higgs boson mass. This method allows for a model-independent measurement of the Higgs boson's coupling to the Z boson, a unique feature of circular colliders like the FCC-ee. This measurement serves as a "standard candle" for other experiments, including those conducted at hadron colliders.

Additionally, the position of the recoil mass peak provides a precise measurement of the Higgs boson mass, thanks to the accurate control of the center-of-mass energy. When combined with the measurement of the rate of HZ events where the Higgs boson decays into a pair of particles, which is

proportional to the Higgs coupling, it allows for a model-independent determination of the Higgs boson's total width. Such precise measurements are not possible with data from hadron colliders, which lack a well-defined initial state. Similar analysis of other Higgs decays also enables the determination of model-independent Higgs partial widths and couplings.

A summary of the expected FCC capabilities, combined (or not) with the HL-LHC projections, is displayed in Table 2, for FCC-ee and for the full FCC-integrated program (FCC-ee and FCC-hh). The complementarity and synergies between lepton machines like the FCC-ee and hadron colliders are particularly well illustrated in this resource.

Once the Higgs coupling to the Z boson is determined through the ZH total cross-section measurement, results from the LHC on relatively rare Higgs decays, such as those into muon pairs ($\mu^+\mu^-$) or Z boson pairs (ZZ), can be turned into absolute measurements by normalizing them to the ZH decay. This approach provides greater statistical power than what could be achieved by the FCC-ee alone. A similar situation arises with the top Yukawa coupling: while it can be measured with high statistical precision at a hadron collider (like the HL-LHC or FCC-hh), it must be normalized using the ttZ process to reduce the impact of dominant theoretical uncertainties. The ttZ process, in turn, relies on the FCC-ee's measurement of top electroweak couplings through tt ($e^+e^- \rightarrow t\bar{t}$) production. Therefore, the FCC-ee not only provides new model-independent measurements but also enhances the precision and model-independence of measurements from past and future hadron colliders. This same principle applies to measurements made at the FCC-ep collider, which offers additional statistical precision for several channels, particularly in processes like WW ($H \rightarrow WW^*$) and ZZ production, but will benefit from the absolute normalization provided by FCC-ee measurements.

Collider	HL-LHC	FCC-ee _{240→365}	FCC-INT
Lumi (ab^{-1})	3	5 + 0.2 + 1.5	30
Years	10	3 + 1 + 4	25
g_{HZZ} (%)	1.5	0.18/0.17	0.17/0.16
g_{HWW} (%)	1.7	0.44/0.41	0.20/0.19
g_{Hbb} (%)	5.1	0.69/0.64	0.48/0.48
g_{Hcc} (%)	SM	1.3/1.3	0.96/0.96
g_{Hgg} (%)	2.5	1.0/0.89	0.52/0.5
$g_{H\tau\tau}$ (%)	1.9	0.74/0.66	0.49/0.46
$g_{H\mu\mu}$ (%)	4.4	8.9/3.9	0.43/0.43
$g_{H\gamma\gamma}$ (%)	1.8	3.9/1.2	0.32/0.32
$g_{HZ\gamma}$ (%)	11	-/10	0.71/0.7
g_{Htt} (%)	3.4	10./3.1	1.0/0.95
g_{HHH} (%)	50	44/33 27/24	3-4
Γ_H (%)	SM	1.1	0.91
BR_{inv} (%)	1.9	0.19	0.024
BR_{EXO} (%)	SM(0.0)	1.1	1

Table 2. The HL-LHC result is obtained by fixing the total Higgs boson width and the $H \rightarrow c\bar{c}$ branching fraction to their Standard Model values, and by assuming no BSM decays. All numbers are in % and indicate 68% C.L. sensitivities. Also indicated are the standalone precision on the total decay width, and the 95% C.L. sensitivity on the “invisible” and “exotic” branching fractions. The precision on the Higgs self-coupling comprises the value extracted from the ZH and $WW \rightarrow H$ cross sections for FCC-ee, with two (top line) or four (lower line) interaction points. The precision for FCC-hh has been updated using the most recent projections from double-Higgs production at FCC-hh.

The capability of FCC-ee to measure the ZH and $WW \rightarrow H$ cross-sections at two different centre-of-mass energies (240 and 365 GeV) offers a 2-to- 4σ sensitivity to the Higgs self-coupling, via a loop diagram. The FCC-ee Higgs and top coupling measurements make it possible to measure the Higgs self-coupling at the 100 TeV collider, with a precision around $\pm 10\%$ within a couple of years running and eventually of $(3\text{stat} \pm 1.6\text{syst})\%$ [26]. For the Higgs measurements, as for many other aspects of the physics program, the combination of FCC-ee and FCC-hh is outstanding [27].

Finally, the FCC-ee distinguishes itself among the various "Higgs Factory" projects with its unique potential to probe the Higgs boson's coupling to electrons [28, 29, 30] through a process known as resonant production at 125 GeV. Achieving this measurement depends on a combination of the collider's high luminosity and the ability to finely tune the beam energies, a technique known as monochromatization. This opportunity is exclusive to the FCC-ee and represents one of its most significant and challenging scientific goals.

2.3.2. Precision measurements

Several experimental observations suggest that the Standard Model of particle physics may need to be extended. These include the dominance of matter over antimatter in the Universe, evidence for dark matter from astronomical and cosmological observations, and, more directly related to particle physics, the extremely small masses of neutrinos—about a million times smaller than that of the electron. Addressing these questions likely requires the existence of new particles or phenomena spanning a vast range of mass scales and interaction strengths.

Historically, the discovery of new particles has often been driven by predictions grounded in a long history of experiments and theoretical developments. In this context, significantly enhancing the precision of electroweak precision observables (EWPO), along with other precise measurements of the properties of the Higgs boson, the top quark, b and c hadrons, and the tau lepton, could be crucial. These measurements could increase sensitivity to a wide range of potential new physics. Observing significant deviations from the Standard Model predictions would constitute a true discovery. Achieving high significance in these findings requires not only substantial improvements in both experimental and theoretical precision but also a broad array of measured observables. This approach helps eliminate false deviations and could reveal a consistent pattern, guiding the theoretical interpretation. Enhanced precision boosts the potential for discovery, but it also presents challenges for both theory and experiment. Table 3 highlights the opportunities and challenges associated with precision measurements.

Observable	present value	\pm	error	FCC-ee Stat.	FCC-ee Syst.	Comment and leading error
m_Z (keV)	91186700	\pm	2200	4	100	From Z line shape scan Beam energy calibration
Γ_Z (keV)	2495200	\pm	2300	4	25	From Z line shape scan Beam energy calibration
$\sin^2 \theta_W^{\text{eff}} (\times 10^6)$	231480	\pm	160	2	2.4	From $A_{\text{FB}}^{\mu\mu}$ at Z peak Beam energy calibration
$1/\alpha_{\text{QED}}(m_Z^2)(\times 10^3)$	128952	\pm	14	3	small	From $A_{\text{FB}}^{\mu\mu}$ off peak QED&EW errors dominate
$R_\ell^Z (\times 10^3)$	20767	\pm	25	0.06	0.2-1	Ratio of hadrons to leptons Acceptance for leptons
$\alpha_s(m_Z^2) (\times 10^4)$	1196	\pm	30	0.1	0.4-1.6	From R_ℓ^Z
$\sigma_{\text{had}}^0 (\times 10^3)$ (nb)	41541	\pm	37	0.1	4	Peak hadronic cross-section Luminosity measurement
$N_\nu (\times 10^3)$	2996	\pm	7	0.005	1	Z peak cross-sections Luminosity measurement
$R_b (\times 10^6)$	216290	\pm	660	0.3	< 60	Ratio of $b\bar{b}$ to hadrons Stat. extrapol. from SLD
$A_{\text{FB},0}^b (\times 10^4)$	992	\pm	16	0.02	1-3	b-quark asymmetry at Z pole From jet charge
$A_{\text{FB}}^{\text{pol},\tau} (\times 10^4)$	1498	\pm	49	0.15	<2	τ polarisation asymmetry τ decay physics
τ lifetime (fs)	290.3	\pm	0.5	0.001	0.04	Radial alignment
τ mass (MeV)	1776.86	\pm	0.12	0.004	0.04	Momentum scale
τ leptonic ($\mu\nu_\mu\nu_\tau$) B.R. (%)	17.38	\pm	0.04	0.0001	0.003	e/ μ /hadron separation
m_W (MeV)	80350	\pm	15	0.25	0.3	From WW threshold scan Beam energy calibration
Γ_W (MeV)	2085	\pm	42	1.2	0.3	From WW threshold scan Beam energy calibration
$\alpha_s(m_W^2)(\times 10^4)$	1010	\pm	270	3	small	From R_ℓ^W
$N_\nu (\times 10^3)$	2920	\pm	50	0.8	small	Ratio of invis. to leptonic in radiative Z returns
m_{top} (MeV)	172740	\pm	500	17	small	From $t\bar{t}$ threshold scan QCD errors dominate
Γ_{top} (MeV)	1410	\pm	190	45	small	From $t\bar{t}$ threshold scan QCD errors dominate
$\lambda_{\text{top}}/\lambda_{\text{top}}^{\text{SM}}$	1.2	\pm	0.3	0.10	small	From $t\bar{t}$ threshold scan QCD errors dominate
ttZ couplings		\pm	30%	0.5 – 1.5 %	small	From $\sqrt{s} = 365$ GeV run

Table 3. Measurement of selected precision measurements at FCC-ee, compared with present precision. Statistical errors are indicated in bold. The systematic uncertainties are initial estimates, aim is to improve down to statistical errors. This set of measurements, together with those of the Higgs properties, achieves indirect sensitivity to new physics up to a scale Λ of 70 TeV in a description with dim 6 operators, and possibly much higher in specific new physics (non-decoupling) models.

The anticipated statistical precision for electroweak precision observables (EWPOs) measured at the Z pole is expected to be up to 500 times more accurate than current measurements. In some cases, the improvements could be even more significant. For instance, there is potential for a direct measurement of the electroweak mixing angle with unprecedented precision for the first time.

The big question is how far experimental and theoretical systematic uncertainties can be reduced to match this level of statistical precision. This challenge represents both an exciting opportunity and a significant hurdle for detector designers and experts in theoretical calculations.

As an example, Figure 5 illustrates the projected uncertainty in the S and T parameters—used to describe isospin-conserving and isospin-breaking virtual effects in the Z and W boson propagators—across different colliders. The left panel shows that FCC-ee measurements at the Z pole, WW threshold, and top-quark production threshold offer the most promising outlook, minimizing parametric uncertainties. The right panel highlights the enormous standalone potential of FCC-ee, assuming future experimental and theoretical systematic uncertainties can match the statistical precision available, which poses a substantial challenge for both experimental and theoretical teams.

Figure 5. Expected uncertainty contour for the S and T parameters for various colliders in their first energy stage. For ILC and CLIC, the projections are shown with and without dedicated running at the Z pole, with the current (somewhat arbitrary) estimate of future experimental and theoretical systematic uncertainty and with only statistical and parametric uncertainties.

The complementarity between the Higgs and Electroweak observables has been investigated in the context of specific heavy new physics, with a global EFT fit, as shown in Fig. 6. This figure, made for FCC-ee only, highlights the complementarity of Higgs and electroweak measurements; the need for more statistics for the (statistics-limited) Higgs measurements; the interest of the Electroweak measurements and of the improvement of the associated systematic uncertainties; and the large number of observables available at FCC-ee.

Figure 6. Electroweak (red) and Higgs (green) constraints from FCC-ee, and their combination (blue) in a global EFT fit. The constraints are presented as the 95% probability bounds on the interaction scale, $\Delta|c_i|$, associated to each EFT operator. Darker shades of each colour indicate the results when neglecting all SM theory uncertainties.

Dedicated analysis of the pattern of deviations for specific models of new physics will be necessary to fully explore the ability of FCC-ee to identify or restrict the origin of one or several experimental deviation(s) from the SM predictions.

2.3.3. Flavours

A total of 7×10^{11} bb^- pairs, available with a sample of 5×10^{12} Z decays promised by FCC-ee, provides many opportunities in flavour physics. The precisions of CKM matrix element measurements expected from LHCb and Belle2 will be challenged, and the search for unobserved phenomena will be pushed forward, such as CP-symmetry breaking in the mixing of beautiful neutral mesons.

In parallel, searches for rare decays make FCC-ee a direct discovery machine. Lepton-flavour-violating (LFV) Z decays; rare and Lepton Flavour Violation (LFCV) τ decays; searches for heavy neutral leptons; and rare b-hadron decays; have been explored in Ref. [14] as benchmark or flagship searches. They are illustrative of the unique potential of a high-luminosity Z factory. The discovery potential relies on the vertexing capabilities of the experiments, to take benefit of the boosted topologies at the Z energy, but is mostly limited by the statistical size of the event sample.

A minimum of 5×10^{12} Z decays has been shown to be necessary to make, for example, a comprehensive study of the rare electroweak penguin transition $b \rightarrow s \tau^+ \tau^-$. If these flavour anomalies do not survive the LHCb and Belle2 future scrutiny, the study of Z couplings to third-generation quarks and leptons still constitute an excellent opportunity to unravel BSM physics. Tau physics at the Z pole provides, still today, the most powerful tests of lepton universality and of the PMNS matrix

unitarity. The increase of statistics by five orders of magnitude with respect to LEP should allow much improvement of these constraints, by combining measurements of the tau lifetime, the tau mass, and the leptonic branching ratios. These measurements provide important constraints on e.g. light-heavy neutrino mixing. Similar improvements are expected from the better precision of the invisible Z decay width measurement. The exploration of the flavour physics program of FCC-ee is certainly in its infancy and can be expected to develop strongly in the future [31].

2.3.4. Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD)

The hadronic Z decays expected at FCC-ee offer invaluable opportunities for in-depth QCD studies at the Z pole [52]. One key area of investigation is the determination of the strong coupling constant, α_s , derived from the ratio of the Z boson's hadronic width to its leptonic width. The sheer volume of data available at FCC-ee significantly enhances the precision of this measurement. With current error estimates, an experimental uncertainty in α_s of just 0.00015 is achievable, with further improvements anticipated in the next phase of detector studies. Similar precision could potentially be achieved from tau decays or from measuring the hadronic and leptonic decay branching ratios of the W boson, which will be abundantly produced when FCC-ee operates at higher center-of-mass energies [22, 32, 33]. Moreover, studying the energy evolution of event shapes and fragmentation functions in e^+e^- collisions offers powerful tests of QCD. The broad range of energies accessible by FCC-ee, starting from as low as 30 GeV [34], will provide an independent and highly precise determination of the strong coupling constant.

Lastly, the Higgs run at FCC-ee presents a unique opportunity: the ability to clearly separate the gg decay mode of the Higgs boson from other hadronic decays, which are expected to be dominated by bb^- and cc^- decays. This capability could create a unique laboratory for studying gluon fragmentation in an environment free from colour connections to quarks.

2.3.5. Direct Observations of Feebly Coupling Particles

Direct observation of new particles might require diverse searches and colliders to cover many orders of magnitude of coupling strength and mass scales. Feebly interacting particles such as axion-like particles, or dark photons, with masses smaller than the Z mass, may have the best odds of being found at the intensity frontier, i.e., with FCC-ee running at the Z pole, while high-energy machines might see them if their couplings are larger. The case of the axion-like particles is illustrated in Fig.7 and demonstrates the high sensitivity of the Z factory FCC-ee, as well as its complementarity with the FCC-eh and with a high-energy linear lepton collider.

Figure 7. Expected sensitivity to axion-like particles in various future facilities. The reach of FCC-ee is down to very small couplings in Z decays, while the reach of linear colliders is at higher masses for somewhat larger couplings.

Another compelling example of new physics involves neutrinos. Many models that explain neutrino masses naturally suggest the existence of heavy neutrino states, known as Heavy Neutral Leptons (HNLs), which are mostly "right-handed" or "sterile" and mix with the familiar light, active neutrinos with a typical mixing angle θ . Since the masses of both light and heavy neutrinos are unknown, a wide range of mixing angles should be investigated. These scenarios have several potential implications:

1. The direct observation of a long-lived HNL in decays of the Z, W, and Higgs bosons, as well as in tau, b-, or c-hadron semi-leptonic decays, where both mass and mixing angle play a crucial role.
2. The mixing of light neutrinos with heavier states, leading to violations of Standard Model (SM) relations in electroweak precision observables (EWPOs); this sensitivity depends solely on the mixing angle and can extend to very high masses.
3. The violation of lepton universality in tau, b, or c-hadron decays at a Z factory.
4. A smaller-than-expected Z boson invisible decay width.
5. The possibility of lepton-number violation due to the production or exchange of Heavy Neutral

Leptons in high-energy processes at a hadron collider or a high-energy lepton collider.

The most sensitive tests for these scenarios, particularly for masses above a few GeV, are conducted at FCC-ee, as illustrated in Fig. 8. These tests could either lead to the direct observation of HNLs or reveal a distinct pattern of deviations from the SM in electroweak and heavy flavour observables.

Figure 8. Left: Illustration of the production of a Heavy Neutral Lepton (HNL) at FCC-ee, followed by its decay approximately 1 meter from the interaction point. Right: Projected sensitivity to Heavy Neutral Leptons (also known as Right-Handed Neutrinos) at various future facilities. FCC-ee's reach extends to extremely small heavy-light mixing angles in Z decays, approaching the see-saw limit. This sensitivity is complemented by constraints from electroweak and tau decay precision measurements, covering masses up to 60 TeV or more for larger heavy-light neutrino mixing.

2.4. CHALLENGES FOR THE DETECTOR DESIGN

Reaching experimental and theoretical systematic uncertainties commensurate to the statistical precision of the many measurements feasible at the FCC-ee requires careful preparation of the detector concepts, possibly of the mode of operation, and of theoretical developments.

2.4.1. Detector Requirements

The wide range of physics measurements and searches at FCC-ee will result in numerous detector requirements, which may be difficult to achieve with just one or even two detector designs. Developing a comprehensive set of specifications and understanding their impact on physics measurements will be a key outcome of the feasibility study. An initial version of these specifications is discussed in Refs. [35, 36]. Below is a brief overview of the types of requirements currently being examined.

For Higgs and top physics at 240 and 340–365 GeV, a set of requirements has been established, particularly focused on particle-flow reconstruction, flavour tagging, and lepton momentum performance, based on previous linear collider studies. However, these need to be adjusted to account for the more favourable operating conditions of the FCC-ee, including a smaller beam-pipe radius and lower maximum operating energy. Additional requirements have emerged, such as the need for a more precise Higgs boson mass determination [35] before the s-channel Higgs production run, and for an accurate ZH cross-section measurement to precisely determine the Higgs self-coupling. The s-channel Higgs production also imposes stringent demands on the monochromatization of the center-of-mass energy, while maintaining high luminosity and enabling sensitive analyses to distinguish Higgs decays from the significant background of lepton-positron annihilation events.

2.4.2. TeraZ Challenges

The high luminosity and large event rate at the Z pole, exceeding 100 kHz, along with the need to process simulated data, pose significant challenges for data collection, storage, and processing. Determining the Z lineshape, which relies on cross-section measurements across different center-of-mass energies for hadronic and leptonic Z decays, demands extremely precise mechanical construction of the luminometer and an accurate understanding of the central detector's acceptance (tracker and/or calorimeter), especially for di-lepton and di-photon events. Additionally, the point-to-point uncertainties in the center-of-mass energy during the resonance scan, verified through muon pair invariant mass reconstruction, are critical for determining the Z width and forward-backward asymmetries. This imposes strict requirements on the stability of momentum reconstruction over time and across scan points.

2.4.3. W Mass Determination

The W mass can be precisely determined through a scan of the WW pair production threshold. Achieving a precision of 0.5 MeV is particularly demanding in terms of center-of-mass energy calibration and the theoretical understanding of the cross-section, rather than the detector itself. However, the calibration of jet angles, and the precise knowledge of hadron composition within these jets, may need to be reassessed. Similarly, precise requirements for lepton angle, energy reconstruction, and energy scale calibration should be established.

2.4.4. Flavour Challenges

The large number of events, coupled with exceptional vertexing capabilities, allows for unprecedented b- and c-tagging performance. The resulting statistical uncertainties in flavour-related electroweak precision observables (EWPOs), such as R_b or (A_{FB}^b) , suggest significant improvements over LEP measurements. Additionally, fully exploiting the rich FCC-ee flavour program requires a detector equipped with hadron identification that covers the effective momentum range at the Z resonance, along with electromagnetic calorimetry offering high-energy resolution.

2.4.5. Tau Physics

The tau measurements—such as lifetime, mass, and branching fractions—have the potential to determine the Fermi constant with exceptional precision. These measurements demand some of the most stringent detector requirements, particularly in terms of momentum resolution (for mass measurements and lepton-flavour violation searches), precise knowledge of vertex detector dimensions (for tau lifetime), and π_K separation across the entire momentum range (for leptonic branching ratios). Moreover, tau-based EWPOs, like $A_{FB\tau}$ and R_τ , as well as detailed studies of hadronic spectral functions, require high granularity and efficiency in both the tracker and electromagnetic calorimeter.

2.4.6. Rare Processes

The current Heavy Neutral Lepton (HNL) search strategy uses a conservative approach, focusing on HNL decays within 1 meter of the interaction point, which reaches just shy of the see-saw limit. Expanding this search to detect HNL decays occurring further from the interaction point, possibly by

utilizing the large cavern space around the detector, could extend the discovery potential. Other feebly interacting particles, which may decay into non-pointing or delayed photons, present a different set of challenges, potentially benefiting from high-precision timing.

2.4.7. Integration Challenges

Integrating all these initial detector requirements into one or even several detectors is a significant challenge, reflecting the unique measurement opportunities and discovery potential offered by FCC-ee. A refined list of detector requirements is being developed through case studies based on physics benchmarks at FCC-ee. The performance of various detector components—such as calorimeters, tracking and vertex detectors, muon detectors, luminometers, and particle identification devices—is being studied to determine how they can meet these rigorous requirements.

2.5. THE CASE FOR FOUR INTERACTION POINTS

One of the great advantages of circular colliders is the ability to serve multiple interaction points, resulting in a net overall gain in both integrated luminosity and luminosity per megawatt. It is expected that a design with four interaction regions could achieve a total facility luminosity that is 1.7 times greater than the scenario with only two interaction points, which has been the focus of studies so far.

The extensive range of physics possibilities at FCC-ee includes precision measurements, sensitivity to feebly-coupled particles, and rare process studies. These opportunities will challenge and shape the field of particle physics for decades to come. There is a genuine chance for new physics discoveries, and such results could significantly influence the design and physics outcomes of the FCC-hh detector. The key to success lies in a combination of high luminosity, redundancy, and careful preparation of detector setups. Many measurements are limited by statistics and would immediately benefit from having four interaction points. Several critical physics targets, such as the Higgs self-coupling and the search for heavy neutral leptons, are tantalizingly close to being within reach with the current two-IP setup. Expanding to four IPs would allow for a broader range of detector solutions, maximizing the FCC-ee's potential for physics discoveries.

Studies already conducted indicate that the diverse detector requirements—such as those for the electromagnetic calorimeter—may not be fully met by just one or even two detectors. The challenges of achieving high precision, granularity, stability, geometric accuracy, particle identification, and cost-effectiveness may be too complex to address all at once. Furthermore, experience from LEP has shown that different detector solutions are invaluable in uncovering hidden systematic biases and avoiding errors, while also providing an exciting challenge for experts across the field of particle physics, including detector technology, design and R&D, computing, software, analysis, and theory.

2.6. THEORETICAL CHALLENGES

The FCC-ee physics program presents several key theoretical challenges, which are discussed in Chapter III of this EPJ+ special issue [37]. Broadly, the goal is to develop tools that allow experimental observations to be compared to theoretical predictions with a precision that matches or exceeds the statistical uncertainties of the experiments, some of which are highlighted in Table 3. Another important objective is to identify additional calculations, tools, observables, or experimental inputs necessary to reach this level of precision. A crucial area of collaboration between theorists and experimentalists involves pinpointing observables, or ratios of observables, where uncertainties—whether experimental or theoretical—can be minimized. Additionally, for prioritization and motivational purposes, it's essential to assess the relative impact of various measurements on the search for new physics. The theoretical work motivated by the FCC program can be organized into several key areas:

3. **Calculation of Corrections:** This involves computing QED, electroweak (EW), and QCD corrections to (differential) cross sections. These corrections are crucial for converting experimental measurements back to "pseudo-observables," such as couplings, masses, partial widths, and asymmetries. These pseudo-observables should closely align with experimental measurements, ensuring that any potential new physics is not obscured. Accurate event generators are vital for incorporating these effects into experimental procedures.
 4. **Precision Calculation of Pseudo-Observables:** In the context of the Standard Model, it's necessary to calculate pseudo-observables with the precision required to fully utilize the experimental data.
 5. **Addressing Limiting Issues:** This includes identifying and addressing the limitations related to parameter definitions, particularly the treatment of quark masses and, more broadly, QCD-related objects.
 6. **Exploring New Physics Sensitivity:** Theoretical work should also investigate how sensitive proposed (or new) experimental observables are to new physics effects in various key scenarios. This work is crucial to undertake early in the project's development, as it can influence the priorities for detector designs and the experimental running plan.
- A significant community of theorists is already engaging with these precision challenges, particularly at the Z peak [38]. An evaluation of future directions and options can be found in Refs. [37, 39, 40].

3. FCC-EE MIDTERM REPORT AND NEXT STEPS

The landscape of particle physics has been profoundly transformed by two major developments: the discovery of the Higgs boson with a mass of 125 GeV and the lack of signs of new physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM) in the TeV range after a decade of LHC operation. These findings have ushered in a new phase of exploration, marked by both clarity and uncertainty.

On one hand, the long-predicted matrix of particles and interactions described by the Standard Model (SM) is now complete. This theory has been remarkably successful in describing all phenomena accessible to collider experiments. However, as we transition into a new era of exploration beyond the SM, there is a notable absence of clear theoretical guidance—a situation unprecedented since the era of the Fermi theory. On the other hand, several fundamental experimental observations remain unexplained within the current framework, such as the matter-antimatter asymmetry, the evidence for dark matter, and the existence of non-zero neutrino masses. These unresolved issues definitively call for new physics beyond the present Standard Model.

The absence of LHC signals for BSM physics in the TeV range necessitates rethinking these open questions. Potential solutions may lie at even higher energy scales, which might require an "unnatural" value of the weak scale or an ingenious but still elusive structure. Recently devised new physics scenarios often involve light and very weakly coupled structures, whose mass scale (ranging from meV to ZeV) and coupling intensity to the SM (from 1 to 10^{-12} or less) remain unknown. This uncertainty calls for a new, comprehensive, and powerful exploration tool.

The FCC (Future Circular Collider) provides this tool by offering considerable advances in sensitivity, precision, and energy far above the TeV scale. Operating initially with electrons and positrons as the finest Higgs factory—and subsequently with protons as the energy-frontier collider—the FCC is designed to meet these challenges. The FCC aims to:

1. Map the properties of the Higgs and electroweak gauge bosons with unprecedented accuracy.
2. Conduct a comprehensive and precise campaign of measurements sensitive to tiny deviations from predicted SM behaviour.
3. Improve sensitivity to rare and elusive phenomena at low-energy scales.
4. Extend the direct discovery reach for new particles at the energy frontier.

From the Fermi interactions to the discovery of the W and Z bosons, and from precision electroweak measurements to the discoveries of the top quark and the Higgs boson, precision has always been a

route to discovery. The FCC will continue this tradition, as any deviations from SM predictions observed at FCC-ee (the electron-positron stage) can be interpreted as indicators of new energy scales to be explored later at FCC-hh (the hadron collider stage).

Midterm Deliverables: Physics and Experiments

1. **Documentation of the Specificities and Complementarity of the FCC-ee and FCC-hh Physics Cases:** This includes detailed characterizations of the SM Higgs boson and the unique opportunities each collider stage offers.
2. **Strategic Plan for Improved Calculations:** To match theoretical uncertainties with the expected statistical precision from FCC-ee measurements.
3. **Preliminary Detector Requirements:** A coherent set of requirements to fully exploit FCC-ee physics opportunities and reduce experimental uncertainties.

Salient Conclusions from the Feasibility Study

The Feasibility Study has yielded several important conclusions:

- The baseline plan includes running at various center-of-mass energies from 90 GeV to 350 GeV, each providing unique and complementary scientific opportunities.
- Adequate flexibility in operation is necessary to accommodate future user community requests and unforeseen discoveries.
- The FCC-ee programme, particularly the TeraZ run, is highly ambitious both scientifically and technically, requiring careful planning and extended periods of data accumulation.
- The combination of FCC-ee and FCC-hh provides the most comprehensive and powerful exploration tool, with significant complementarity between the precision measurements at FCC-ee and the discovery potential at FCC-hh.

4. CONCLUSION

The FCCIS project's Physics Research Programme represents a strategic and well-coordinated effort to push the frontiers of particle physics.

Experimentation at FCC-ee is both relatively straightforward and highly challenging. The experimental conditions are favourable, with clean data free from pile-up, a well-defined and controllable center-of-mass energy, and minimal effects from beamstrahlung and synchrotron radiation.

However, the challenges arise from the extensive scope of the program, which involves studying 10^{12} Z bosons (including 10^{11} muon pairs, tau pairs, and b(c) quark pairs), 10^8 W pairs, 10^6 ZH events, and 10^5 top quark events.

Achieving the necessary experimental and theoretical precision to match the statistical accuracy, and configuring the detector to handle the wide variety of channels and potential discoveries, might seem like an impossible task. Yet, for the dedicated group of creative enthusiasts ready to take on these exciting challenges, nothing will be impossible.

This work culminated in the final chapter of the FCC Feasibility Study Midterm report that is published on CDS: <https://repository.cern/records/511pr-rd590>. Full access to the report can be given upon request to members of EC and reviewers of the project.

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